

Florida Puerto Rico District of ITE
2021 Summer Meeting Preliminary Program

ROAD TO RECOVERY:
Exploring Opportunities for Safety, Mobility, and Innovation

Wednesday, June 23, 2021

1:00 PM - 5:00 PM	Registration Opens
1:00 PM - 5:00 PM	FLPRITE Board Meeting
3:30 PM - 6:00 PM	Technical Tour (TBD)
6:00 PM - 7:00 PM	Meet-and-Greet at the Hotel (Dinner on your own)

Thursday, June 24, 2021

7:30 AM - 3:00 PM	Registration Opens
7:30 AM - 8:30 AM	Breakfast
8:30 AM - 10:00 AM	<p>Introductory Remarks by Vishal Kakkad, PE, PTOE, RSP1 (Manatee County, FLPRITE President) and Elizabeth Biriel, PE, PTOE (Leidos, FLPRITE Immediate Past President)</p> <p>Road to Recovery by FDOT D4 Secretary Gerry O'Reilly, PE; FDOT D6 Secretary Stacy Miller, PE; and Florida Turnpike Enterprise Executive Director & CEO Nicola Liquori</p>
10:00 AM - 10:30 AM	Networking Break
10:30 AM - 12:00 PM	<p>Technical Session Track 1: From Planning to Operations Moderator: Catalina Echeverri, PMP (Gannett Fleming, FLPRITE Vice President)</p> <p>Joseph DeFronzo, PE, RSP1 (City of Port St Lucie) - Low-Cost Improvements to Proven Safety Countermeasures: What's in Your Toolbox? Larry Hagen, PE, PTOE, RSP1 (Hagen Consulting Services LLC) - Retroreflectivity: Why it Matters Paula Flores (GPI) - Vision Zero Hillsborough - Speed Management Action Plan Matt Weissman, PE (Ultra Engineering) - International Traffic Engineering Experience</p>
	<p>Technical Session Track 2: Innovation for Every Day Mobility Moderator: Alexandra Lopez, PE, PTOE (FDOT District 4)</p> <p>V.Y. "Trey" Tillander, III, PE (FDOT Central Office) - FDOT Traffic Operations Updates Yamilet Diaz, PE (FDOT District 6) - Keys COAST Alejandro Motta, PE (FDOT District 6) - Managing a Real-Time Traffic Operations Program During a Pandemic</p>
12:00 PM - 1:30 PM	<p>Lunch with ITE International President Alyssa Rodriguez, PE, PTOE; ITE International Vice President Beverly Kuhn, PhD, PE, PMP; and Vice President-Elect Rosana Correa, PE, PTOE</p>
1:30 PM - 3:00 PM	<p>Technical Session Track 1: Traffic Engineering 2.0 Moderator: Kris Milster, PE, PTOE (NoTraffic, FLPRITE Secretary)</p> <p>Tom Creasy, PhD, PE (Caliper Corporation) - Integration of Safety Analysis Tools into Microsimulation Software Erin Emmons, GISP and Stewart Robertson, PE (Kimley-Horn and Associates) - Shifting from Level of Service to Vehicle Miles Traveled: A Real-World Case Study Anita Vandervalk, PE, PMP (Iteris) - The Future Role of Data in Intersection Management - Safety and Mobility Perspectives Chris Russo, PE, PTOE (Atkins) - Recruiting the Next Generation of Traffic Engineers</p>
	<p>Technical Session Track 2: Advanced Multimodal Solutions Moderator: Bob Agrusa, PE, PTOE (TEDS, FLPRITE Transportation and Mobility Council Chair)</p> <p>Rawad Hani, PE, PTOE, RSP1 (General Technologies and Solutions) - Vehicle Miles Traveled: Practitioners Challenges and Opportunities Eric Katz, AICP and Jeff Weidner (Marlin Engineering) - Innovations in Non-Motorized Traffic Data Collection and Reporting Jodi Godfrey (Center for Urban Transportation Research) - Improving Transit Passengers Safety Scott Belcher (SFB Consulting) - Innovative Intersections Michael Clance (Q-Free America) - Unifying Signal and Freeway Management</p>
3:00 PM - 3:30 PM	Networking Break
3:30 PM - 5:00 PM	<p>Moving Southeast Florida's Transportation System Forward Moderator: Steven Abrams, Executive Director SFRTA</p> <p>Aileen Bouclé, AICP, Executive Director Miami-Dade Transportation Planning Organization (TPO); Greg Stuart, AICP, Executive Director Broward Metropolitan Planning Organization (MPO); Nick Uhren, PE, Executive Director Palm Beach Transportation Planning Agency (TPA)</p>
	<p>Closing Remarks: Vishal Kakkad, PE, PTOE, RSP1 (Manatee County, FLPRITE President)</p>
5:30 PM - 7:30 PM	Reception by the Beach co-hosted with ASCE